

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The school-community partnership and performance in numeracy of secondary schools

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Abstract

This study examined the school-community partnership and numeracy performance of secondary schools in Tabaco City Division for SY 2022-2023. It explored activities involving schools and communities, assessed partnership levels in Project ANGLE and Brigada Matematika, and evaluated school numeracy performance. Using a descriptive survey, it tested the relationship between school-community partnership and numeracy outcomes, identified challenges, and proposed an action plan for improvement. Respondents included school heads, teachers, and community partners, with data analyzed through frequency count, percentage, weighted mean, Pearson r, and t-test to determine trends and correlations in numeracy performance and collaborative engagement.

This study highlighted the effectiveness of school-community partnerships in improving numeracy performance in Tabaco City Division, particularly through Project ANGLE and Brigada Matematika. The findings showed a strong collaboration between schools and communities, leading to near mastery levels in numeracy, though challenges such as limited resources and inconsistent stakeholder engagement persist. A significant correlation was found between partnership strength and numeracy outcomes, emphasizing the need for sustained collaboration, adequate funding, and teacher training. To enhance program sustainability, schools are encouraged to strengthen stakeholder engagement, allocate sufficient resources, and implement the proposed action plan for long-term improvements in numeracy education.

Keywords: Project ANGLE; Numeracy Performance; Long-Term Improvement in Numeracy; Numeracy education

1. Introduction

In the continuing scenery of educational excellence, the collaboration between schools and their communities has emerged as a crucial support for enhancing student performance and institutional effectiveness. School-community partnerships play an important role in successful schools and it is vital in strengthening numeracy performance.

The importance of numeracy is echoed in the Sustainable Development Goals, particularly in Goal 4, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities. This global agenda sets the stage for local entities to enact policies and forge partnerships that directly impact numeracy education. Increased community partners' participation in school administration and management, as well as in academic discourse, is a current phenomenon. As a result, education is intended to serve as a platform for the integration of ideas from various partners within the school community. If partners are not actively involved in school administration and management, the school may be unable to bridge the gap between what the community wants and what the school intends to achieve.

At the global level, school-community partnerships are underpinned by a commitment to inclusive education, as evidenced by various international conventions and declarations.¹ These global commitments provide a broad canvas

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upon which individual nations paint their localized legal structures, tailoring School Community Partnership (SCP) frameworks to align with cultural, societal, and educational needs.

In the Philippines, the legal basis for School-Community Partnerships is strong, anchored on Republic Act No.10533, known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, which mandates the establishment of school-community networks and active participation of various stakeholders in the educational process.² This act, alongside other policies such as the Department of Education's Order No. 40, s. 2015³, which outlines guidelines for K to 12 partnerships, creates a conducive environment for School Community Partnerships (SCPs) to flourish, ultimately aiming to uplift the quality of education and student outcomes. Likewise, the legal framework fosters such collaborations, with the Department of Education emphasizing the significance of community involvement in enhancing learning outcomes, especially in strengthening quality performance in numeracy.⁴

The community and the school are two interdependent structures, which should support each other. The community and the school should work together. The principles of partnership and cooperation are part of the solutions to the problem. Educators should encourage the community to participate in the smooth running of the school. They should also recognize the importance of the community in dealing with community-based problems. Sound relationships between the community and the school should be promoted.

This partnership is significant primarily for the success of its articulation of school, home, and community sectors in pursuit of better educational outcomes for children. This program demonstrates the truth of arguments in the literature that success depends on sustained mutual collaboration, support, and participation of education personnel and families at home and school. There is also a substantial and unusual sharing of decision-making power between teachers, Technical Support Offices (TSOs), and the community. Although this program has been in operation for a relatively short time, it depends on exactly those sorts of relationships built up over many years. It demonstrates that such essential relationships cannot be mandated from outside nor built up overnight but depend on trust and mutual respect which can only be gained over time.

Moreover, a partnership is the product of collaborative processes within an inter-organizational network and successful partnerships lead to the creation of a "second-order organization". Essentially, when a group of individuals makes joint decisions, embraces collaboration, and forms strategic alliances they are in effect acting as a new organization.

As DepEd continuously finds ways to solve the challenges faced by Philippine education, a partnership has become an important paradigm in delivering and achieving the country's development goals and services. Through partnership, the school communities work together to provide additional resources to address the immediate needs of the learners. The collaboration of all education stakeholders and partners is the key to ensuring that our dream of having quality education for all shall be achieved.⁵

Pursuant to DepEd Order No. 013, s. 2023⁶, the Department of Education (DepEd) adopted the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) which aims to strengthen the learning recovery and continuity program, improve literacy and numeracy, and accelerate the achievement of education targets. This DepEd order provides guidelines on the transition plan for the implementation of the K-12 program, specifically for the Grade 7 entrants in the school year 2012-2013.

In the Philippines, to achieve the Education for All (EFA) objectives by 2015, the Department of Education is pursuing policy reforms under the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA). Key Reform Thrust 1 (KRT1) of BESRA is School-Based Management (SBM). SBM underscores the empowerment of key partners in school communities to enable them to actively participate in the continuous improvement of schools towards attaining higher pupil/student learning outcomes.

Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) result indicates Philippine education system is 5 to 6 years behind" according to the Department of Education (2022)⁷. The Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries globally in the student assessment conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) for 15-year-old learners. In the 2022 student assessment, the country scored approximately 120 points lower than the average scores, with scores of 355 in Math, 347 in Reading, and 373 in Science.

In addition, the Department of Education has stepped out of its box from a centralized educational system that believed one size fits all to make education very important to society, particularly to learners. According to Republic Act No. 10533⁸, known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, the Department of Education implements programs,

projects and activities to ensure access to and improve the quality of basic education. It seeks to improve school-based management by devolving education governance to its educational stakeholders.

The importance of building educational partnerships between schools and communities is increasingly acknowledged since community involvement in education is thought to be associated with learners' success at school. With this perspective, and with particular emphasis on the activities where school and community are involved, the Schools Division Office of Tabaco City issued the Division Memorandum No. 96, s. 2022⁹, - the conduct of PROJECT ANGLE (Assessment in Numeracy to Gain Learning) which aimed to determine the non-numerates from Grades 1-11 of the public schools for appropriate intervention.

Likewise, Division Memorandum No. 352, s. 2023¹⁰, known as the Implementation of BRIGADA MATEMATIKA, aimed to make every Tabaqueño learner numerate and teachers competent in teaching concepts in Math; encourage community volunteers to join BRIGADA MATEMATIKA; and increase awareness and understanding of the importance of numeracy and LOVE of numbers. The researcher elaborates a framework for determining the different projects and activities implemented by all secondary schools and for analyzing the extent of the level of school-community partnership in numeracy, the key problems encountered in school-community partnerships, and its effect on the level of performance in numeracy.

Moreover, the Department of Education has programs that community partners are involved in like; the Child-Friendly School System (CFSS). Through this project, students engage in more active participation among fellow students and other school staff: teachers become more active as agents for students' protection, and parents become involved in school activities; the Brigada Eskwela, demonstrates how the communities could work in teams to maintain public schools. Still another in Adopt-A-School Programs formalized by RA No. 8525¹¹. The program is DepEd's vehicle to mobilize support from private and non-government sectors. Based on a menu of assistance packages developed by DepEd, interested companies can sponsor certain school programs/projects. The enactment act of Republic Act No. 9155¹², otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, gave added driving force to the earlier efforts of the Department of Education to decentralize the governance of Basic Education at the grassroots level, however, partners and the community seems to lack awareness on their roles resulting to being inactive into school's activities

2. Conclusion

School-community partnerships are essential for strengthening numeracy education, fostering collaboration, and enhancing student success. In the Philippines, legal frameworks such as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 support the development of structured partnerships to improve learning outcomes. Despite these efforts, challenges such as limited resources, stakeholder engagement, and sustainability must be addressed through strategic action plans. Effective partnerships require active community involvement, continuous support, and mutual trust built over time. Strengthening cooperation between schools, educators, and stakeholders will ensure more equitable, sustainable educational opportunities for all learners.

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